

Assessing the Potential Utility of Large Language Models for Assisting Community Healthcare Workers

A Prospective, Observational Trial in Rwanda

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

List of acronyms	3
Abstract	4
Background	4
Study objectives	5
Methods	6
Ethical considerations	14
Logistics	16
References	18
Appendices	20
Appendix 1: LLM Workflow and Prompt	20
Appendix 2: Information and Written Consent Form - CHW (English)	21
Appendix 3: Information and Written Consent Form - CHW (Kinyarwanda)	23
Appendix 4: Information and Written Consent Form - Patient (English)	25
Appendix 5: Information and Written Consent Form - Patient (Kinyarwanda)	27
Appendix 6: Evaluation Panel Rubric	29
Appendix 7: Follow-Up Tool	33
Appendix 8: Counter-Referral Form	34
Appendix 9: User Experience Questions to Patients (English)	35
Appendix 10: User Experience Questions to Patients (Kinyarwanda)	36
Appendix 11: User Experience Questions to CHWs (English)	37
Appendix 12: User Experience Questions to CHWs (Kinyarwanda)	38

LIST OF ACRONYMS

AI	artificial intelligence
C4IR	Centre for the Fourth Industrial Revolution
CHW	community health worker
CHWApp	Community Health Worker Application
FN	false negative
FP	false positive
LLM	large language model
LMIC	low- and middle-income country
MINICT	Ministry of Information Communication Technology and Innovation
MOH	Ministry of Health
NPV	negative predictive value
PIN	participant identification number
PPV	positive predictive value
RBC	Rwanda Biomedical Centre
SMS	Short Message Service
TN	true negative
TP	true positive
UGHE	University of Global Health Equity

ABSTRACT

A lack of formal clinical training often limits the effectiveness of community health workers (CHWs) and, thus, their ability to generate timely and accurate insights based on the information shared with them. Integrating large language models (LLMs) into the CHWs' workflow presents a novel opportunity to enhance their decision-making capabilities by providing real-time, context-specific, and evidence-based guidance. This non-interventional study aims to explore whether LLMs can support more effective decision-making. After an interaction between a CHW and a patient, the LLM will analyze the recorded conversation to determine the appropriateness of referral decisions made by CHWs compared to the LLM against the clinical expert panel consensus. The study also assesses the feasibility and appropriateness of an LLM-based clinical decision support system for CHWs. The results will inform future research, including the need for an interventional trial of such a product.

BACKGROUND

A community health worker (CHW) is a nonprofessional community member who serves as a frontline health care provider within their neighborhood (Kane et al., 2016; National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute, 2014). CHWs are vital in delivering primary health care services, including disease prevention, health promotion, and recovery support, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) where access to medical professionals is often limited (National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute, 2014; World Health Organization, 2020). While they may not have formal medical training, CHWs use their community knowledge and targeted training to bridge the gap between formal health care systems and their communities (World Health Organization, 2020).

In Rwanda, CHWs are integral to the health care system, offering essential maternal and child health services, infectious disease management, and health education. Their role primarily focuses on triaging, diagnosing, and treating a limited number of common health conditions (CHW Central, 2020; Rwanda Ministry of Health, 2023; Schurer et al., 2020; World Health Organization, 2023). The standard of care for new complaints is guided by a decision algorithm specific to Rwandan CHWs. The algorithm guides CHWs through a series of pre-set questions, prompts necessary actions, and concludes with a recommendation of a referral if needed. The algorithm recommends care and follow-up in the community for patients not requiring referrals. After referrals, CHWs are informed of the patient's medical management through counter referrals from health centers (Rwanda Ministry of Health, 2013).

While CHWs have effectively addressed basic health needs, their lack of formal clinical training limits their ability to manage the increasing complexity of health issues in rural communities (Kane et al., 2016; Olaniran et al., 2022). Thus, the decision protocols used by CHWs in Rwanda are relatively blunt tools, limited in the number of conditions they consider, and typically use closed-ended questions with binary answers. As a result, emerging health concerns such as mental health and new public health threats often go unrecognized or untreated at the community level (Boyce & Katz, 2019; Miller et al., n.d.). This leads to health issues being identified at later stages, resulting in delayed and/or unnecessary referrals, poor health outcomes, and increased costs to the health care system and communities (Lal et al., 2016).

Digital health transformation strategy

As part of Rwanda's digital health transformation strategy, the Rwanda Biomedical Centre (RBC) and the Ministry of Health developed the Community Health Worker Application (CHWApp), a smartphone-based digital decision-support tool to support CHWs in managing a range of health-related complaints by providing functionalities including access to patient health records, scheduling, and health guidelines from the national curriculum for CHWs (including infectious diseases, and child growth monitoring). A pilot of the app ran from February to August 2024 and is now being rolled out nationwide, phasing out paper-based forms and guidelines. As of December 2024, 1,500 CHWs across Rwanda, representing 2.5% of the 60,000 CHWs in Rwanda, were using the CHWApp. However, the protocols and procedures followed by the CHWs have not changed during this initial digital transition period. As it currently stands, for CHWs using the CHWApp, referrals are made using a free text summary in the CHWApp, which is sent via Short Message Service (SMS) to the health center; for CHWs not using the CHWApp, a paper form is provided to the patient, who takes it with them to the health center.

In parallel to the rollout of the CHWApp, the Rwandan Government has begun exploring the value of novel artificial intelligence (AI) tools for improving community health care quality. Large language models (LLMs), like OpenAI's GPT, are AI systems trained on vast linguistic datasets (Ivanov & Penchev, 2024), enabling applications across various fields, including health care, where they are being explored for clinical decision support and workflow optimization (Busch et al., 2025; Meng et al., 2024). While LLMs may assist clinicians by analyzing medical data, improving diagnostic accuracy, and recommending evidence-based treatments (Thirunavukarasu et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2025), their effectiveness has primarily been studied in high-income settings and remains to be fully validated in other health care contexts (Restrepo et al., 2024). Integrating LLMs into CHWs' workflow could improve decision-making capabilities by providing real-time, context-specific, and evidence-based guidance. Based on the growing experience of health care professionals using LLMs, these tools could improve CHW performance by improving the accuracy of diagnoses and referrals of existing protocolized conditions, potentially enabling them to recognize and manage a wider range of conditions.

The study aims to support the Rwandan Government's agenda by exploring whether LLMs can effectively assist CHW health interactions in Rwanda. By comparing the performance of a locally trained LLM with CHWs and clinicians, we aim to shed light on the accuracy and appropriateness of LLMs to support health care in low-resource communities.

STUDY OBJECTIVES

Primary objective

Compare the appropriateness of CHW referral decisions versus the LLM referral decisions, using the referral decision (ground truth) of a panel of clinical experts who have reviewed the day 0 interaction transcript as the reference standard.

Secondary objectives

1. Compare the appropriateness of CHW referral decisions versus the LLM referral decisions, using the patient's 5- or 14-day outcome as the reference standard.
2. Assess the diagnostic accuracy of the LLM as:
 - The appropriateness of the differential diagnosis list.
 - Diagnostic accuracy (top-1 and top-5 diagnosis) in cases with a diagnostic label.
3. Assess the appropriateness of the LLM-generated management plan.
4. Explore the experience and perspectives of patients and CHWs on being recorded during consultation.

Study description

This prospective observational study design will evaluate the accuracy of CHWs' and LLMs' referral decision-making. A standard consultation between a CHW and a patient will be audio-recorded. The recording will then be translated to an English transcript using Kinyarwanda-to-English translator AI and provided to an LLM with prompts to produce differential diagnoses, a referral decision, and a management plan.

A panel of independent evaluators will assess each patient interaction using a pre-specified study-specific evaluation rubric to assess the appropriateness of the CHWs' and LLMs' referral decisions. This study will also evaluate the quality of the LLM outputs in different domains to determine primary evidence of whether LLMs can enhance CHW services.

Study setting

This study will be conducted in Rwanda's Nyabihu, Gicumbi, and Rwamagana districts in the northwest, central, and southeastern parts. These districts were purposely selected from 10 districts where the RBC has equipped CHWs with smartphones. They represent diverse geographic and socio-economic contexts, encompassing both rural and semi-urban populations, and provide a relevant setting for addressing the health care challenges and opportunities found across Rwanda.

Study design

A prospective, observational study design will be used.

Study participants

COMMUNITY HEALTH WORKERS

CHWs who have been provided smartphones by RBC/Ministry of Health will be considered in the study.

Inclusion criteria for CHWs

- CHWs who have completed the RBC's curriculum training.
- CHWs with a minimum of three months' experience in practice.
- CHWs who are able to speak and write in English or Kinyarwanda.

Exclusion criteria for CHWs

- CHWs who have been out of service for more than one month.
- CHWs who are planning to travel or relocate during the time of the study.

A list of all eligible CHWs living in the study districts will be developed. Using the Excel RAND function, 150 CHWs will be randomly selected.

PATIENT PARTICIPANTS

Any patients seeking consultation with a CHW will be considered for this study regardless of gender and age.

Inclusion criteria for patient participants

- The first presentation of any health-related complaint.
- The patient is physically present at the consultation.

Exclusion criteria for patient participants

- Patients receiving CHW visits for reasons other than new health-related complaints (for example, weight checks, vaccinations, routine antenatal care).
- Patients requiring immediate/emergency medical care (for example, trauma, medical emergency).
- The patient/carer is not verbally communicative.
- The patient consultation environment does not allow audio recording.
- The patient does not speak Kinyarwanda or English.
- The patient is unable or unwilling to be contacted for follow-up outcome.
- The patient is unable or unwilling to attend a health center if referred.

Sampling

An appropriate sample size for the external evaluation of the sensitivity and specificity performance of the LLM was derived using the calculations from Whittle et al. (2024). This approach required input of the anticipated performance of the app, which were not well estimated in previous literature. To accurately estimate a range of feasible model performances while maintaining a referral rate of 48.7% (as observed in a previous assessment of referrals in a representative district), we calculated the necessary sample size with a confidence interval of 0.1. We determined that a sample size of 790 interactions (approximately 385 referrals) is required to estimate sensitivity accurately. Given the expected range of 7 to 15 consultations per CHW per week, with 3 to 4 referrals, this sample size is attainable within the study period. Considering a 10% margin for faulty data, we estimate that a total of 869 recordings will be needed.

Data collection procedures

FOREGROUND PROCEDURE (FIELDWORK)

CHW enrollment and training

The RBC and district authorities will facilitate the recruitment of CHWs. Selected CHWs will be contacted via phone by research assistants, who will explain the nature of the study and read the informed consent form. If the CHW agrees to participate, they will be appointed to their local health center on a specified date, where research assistants will again provide the informed consent form and obtain written consent (See Appendix 2 for the English version of the consent form and Appendix 3 for the Kinyarwanda version).

The research team will modify and utilize the CHWApp already used for recording. After obtaining written consent, the research team will install the modified CHWApp on the CHW phones. The CHW participants will receive two days of training from the research team. The training will include instructions and practice sessions on operating the modified CHWApp, patient selection criteria, basic data security, ethical considerations, obtaining informed consent, patient-caregiver professionalism, and privacy. The second day of the training will incorporate simulations to familiarize CHWs with the modifications of the CHWApp practically, practice obtaining informed consent, and get feedback. CHWs will also be instructed to conduct patient outcome follow-up visits to determine changes in the patient's chief complaint. Investigators' contact numbers for queries relating to study procedures will be available to CHWs for the duration of the study.

Patient enrollment and follow-up

CHWs will lead patient enrollment. CHWs will identify and recruit patients who meet the selection criteria during regular consultations. Before starting the consultation, the CHW will explain and provide the informed consent form, including the study's purpose, the voluntary nature of participation, benefits, risks, and the right to refuse or withdraw consent without any repercussions or loss of benefits (Appendix 5). The CHW will then invite the patient to participate. If the patient does not agree to participate, the CHW will continue the consultation without starting to audio-record. If the patient agrees to participate, written consent will be obtained. After obtaining written consent, the CHW will begin recording and proceed with the consultation as usual. The modified CHWApp will silently record and automatically upload the interaction to the Centre for the Fourth Industrial Revolution (C4IR) data warehouse in Kigali. After the consultation, the CHW will ask questions to assess the patient's experience being recorded.

CHWs will conduct a 5-day follow-up (as part of their standard of care) and a 14-day follow-up (as part of a research visit) for all of their patients to document any changes in their health status and subsequent health care interventions. Outcome data collected at these follow-ups will include patient symptom status (i.e., resolved, unchanged, worsened, deceased). CHWs will collect counter-referrals from the health center detailing the patient's presentation, investigation results, diagnosis, and management plan for all patients referred to the health center.

The follow-up will be conducted using a questionnaire on the modified CHWApp. Additionally, a picture of the counter-referral will be uploaded to the app. To avoid repetition, patients who report complete symptom resolution by day 5 will not be followed up on day 14.

The flow of activities for study participants is shown in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1: Study participant flow

After the data collection period, research assistants will appoint CHWs to nearby health centers to conduct short user experience surveys and four focus group discussions of 8 to 12 CHWs to get insight into their experience of being recorded and any challenges faced.

BACKGROUND PROCEDURE (DATA MANAGEMENT)

The recording and transcript will be automatically uploaded and accessed on the C4IR data warehouse. The first 10 to 20 transcript samples will be considered a pilot and excluded from the primary analysis. Instead, they will be used to assess recording quality and transcription accuracy, perform exploratory analysis, and prompt engineering of the LLM. This process will involve examining the initial transcripts to optimize the LLM's performance in generating useful outputs and refining how the prompts are structured to elicit the most accurate and relevant responses. By testing and adjusting the prompt structures based on these transcripts, we will effectively 'tune' the LLM to improve its clinical decision-making capabilities.

Following this, the research team will omit the interaction's outcomes (i.e., the CHW's management and referral decision) and feed the transcript and prompts to the LLM to:

1. Produce a referral decision
2. Suggest five differential diagnoses in order of likelihood.
3. Propose a management plan.

Nine independent general practitioners, each with a minimum of three years of clinical experience in Rwanda and valid Rwanda Medical and Dental Council licenses, will be recruited for this study. They will be organized into three panels to evaluate each patient-CHW consultation transcript using a study-specific evaluation rubric (Appendix 6). This evaluation will provide a ground truth against which the LLM and CHW outputs will be measured. Evaluators will receive training to standardize the evaluation approach. This training will include an overview of the study protocol and detailed instructions on using the evaluation rubric. During the training, 10 cases will be reviewed to establish a common frame of reference across the panel and to familiarize evaluators with the rubric.

Everyone in the triplet group of evaluators will independently review the case transcript, make a diagnosis, and develop a management plan. The evaluator's tasks for each objective are as follows:

1. Based only on the day 0 consultation transcript, a reference standard should be determined to decide on the appropriateness of the CHW and LLM referral decisions.
2. Review the day 0 consultation transcript and the 5- or 14-day follow-up information to establish a reference standard for evaluating the correctness of the CHW and LLM referral decisions.
3. Assess the diagnostic accuracy of the LLM through:
 - Establishing one "most likely" diagnosis based on all the information provided.
 - Independently scoring the appropriateness of the differential diagnosis list according to a pre-specified rubric (Appendix 6).
 - Assessing whether the diagnosis provided in the counter-referral (or, if unavailable, the panel's 'most likely' diagnosis) is the top-ranked or is included within the top five differential diagnoses suggested by the LLM.
4. Assess the appropriateness of the LLM-generated management plan according to the evaluation rubric (Appendix 6).

After the initial assessments, the average response for the Likert scale question will be calculated. The panel will also review and discuss the open-ended responses, such as the 'most likely' diagnosis, and collaboratively reach a consensus on the diagnosis.

Quality assurance

The quality and completeness of study data will be monitored for thoroughness, timeliness, accuracy, and adherence to protocols. CHW participants will receive training during the onboarding session to ensure high-quality data entry. Biweekly data quality audits will be conducted throughout the study to provide feedback to CHW participants and implement any necessary modifications. Additionally, periodic audits of evaluator assessments will be carried out to maintain consistency and accuracy in grading.

To ensure the accuracy and reliability of our transcripts, we will conduct a cross-validation of the patient interaction audio recordings and their corresponding machine-generated English-translated text transcripts. A team of independent researchers, fluent in Kinyarwanda, will review a random sample of 20% of the recordings. They will compare the audio content to the machine-generated transcripts, noting discrepancies or errors. An error rate higher than 15% will prompt a data quality review by the study steering committee to determine whether data collection should continue or changes are required. This approach will enhance the integrity of our data, providing a strong basis for subsequent analysis.

Measures

PRIMARY OUTCOME

The primary outcome is the appropriateness of CHW versus LLM referral decisions.

The outcome measure (appropriateness of referral decision of CHW and LLM) will be determined by measuring concordance with the ground truth suggested by the expert clinical panel (reference standard), according to the day 0 consultation transcript only. Confusion matrices will be constructed to compare accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) for CHW and LLM.

SECONDARY OUTCOMES

Concordance between expert panel referral decision (day 0 plus follow-up consultation transcript) and CHW and LLM referral decisions

The outcome measure (appropriateness of referral decision of CHW and LLM) will be determined by measuring concordance with the ground truth suggested by the expert clinical panel (reference standard), according to the day 0 consultation transcript, along with the 5- or 14-day follow-up outcome. Confusion matrices will be constructed to compare accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and NPV for CHW and LLM.

Diagnostic accuracy of the LLM

APPROPRIATENESS OF DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS LIST

First, an evaluation panel will evaluate the LLM's differential diagnosis list using a pre-specified study-specific rubric, with each domain scored on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from incorrect to highly accurate (Appendix 6):

- Alignment with medical consensus
- Knowledge recall
- Omission of important differential diagnoses
- Inclusion of irrelevant differential diagnoses

ACCURACY OF DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSES

Second, for the subset of cases where a clinical diagnosis can be made (i.e., where all three evaluation panel members agree on the top diagnosis or where a diagnosis was made at the health center), this outcome measures the accuracy of the differential diagnoses in the LLM's output. This will be measured as:

- **Top-1 accuracy:** The percentage of cases where the diagnosis (definitive or consensus diagnosis) is the top-1 diagnosis on the LLM's differential list.
- **Top-5 accuracy:** The percentage of cases in which the diagnosis (definitive or consensus diagnosis) appears in the top-5 differentials of the LLM's output.

Appropriateness of the management plan by the LLM

This outcome assesses the appropriateness of the management plan outlined in the LLM output. This will be assessed using a predefined rubric, with each domain scored on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from incorrect to highly accurate (Appendix 6):

- Alignment with medical consensus
- Omission of important information
- Potential for demographic bias
- Possible likelihood of harm
- Contextual appropriateness of instructions

Statistical analysis plan

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

Descriptive statistics will be used to summarize the demographic characteristics of participants and key measures.

The primary analysis will involve (i) assessing the LLM's performance (accuracy) in relation to the ground truth and (ii) assessing the LLM's accuracy compared to the CHW's performance alone. Model performance will be assessed using the following metrics, discussed in more detail below: accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and NPV.

All model performance metrics and their corresponding confidence intervals will be calculated from information on numbers of true positive (TP), false negative (FN), false positive (FP), and true negative (TN) model allocations included in the standard 2x2 (confusion) matrix, as shown in Table 1. Note here that the term "positive" indicates a decision to refer the patient, and the term "true" indicates that this decision was appropriate.

Table 1. Confusion matrix used in statistical analysis.

SOURCE	DECISION	PANEL DECISION – APPROPRIATE REFERRAL RESPONSE		
		Referral	No referral	
LLM-enabled	Referral	True positive (TP)	False positive (FP)	TP+FP
CHWApp	No referral	False negative (FN)	True negative (TN)	FN+TN
		TP+FN	FP+TN	Total number of observations (N)

Performance metrics:

- **Accuracy** is simply the proportion of appropriate referral decisions made by the LLM-enabled CHWApp. It is calculated as the total number of correct referral allocations (both decisions to refer and not to refer) out of the total number of consultations conducted, as follows:

$$Accuracy = \frac{\text{Number of correct predictions}}{\text{Total number of predictions}} = \frac{TP + TN}{N}$$

$$SE_{acc} = \sqrt{\frac{accuracy \times (1 - accuracy)}{N}}$$

- **Sensitivity** (otherwise known as recall) refers to the probability that someone who should have been referred, according to the ground truth panel decision, was appropriately referred by the LLM-enabled CHWApp. This is calculated by dividing the number of appropriate referrals by the total number of people who should have been referred based on the panel's consensus:

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

$$SE_{recall} = \sqrt{\frac{recall \times (1 - recall)}{TP + FN}}$$

- **Specificity** refers to the probability that someone who should not have been referred was appropriately not referred by the LLM-enabled CHWApp. This is calculated as the number of appropriate non-referrals out of the total number of people who should not have been referred, per the ground truth panel decision:

$$Specificity = \frac{TN}{TN + FP}$$

$$SE_{spec} = \sqrt{\frac{specificity \times (1 - specificity)}{TN + FP}}$$

- **PPV** (otherwise known as **precision**) refers to the probability that the decision to refer a patient was appropriate. It is calculated as the proportion of people who were appropriately referred by the LLM-enabled CHWApp out of the total number of people for whom the app recommended referral:

$$PPV (Precision) = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

$$SE_{prec} = \sqrt{\frac{precision \times (1 - precision)}{TP + FP}}$$

- **NPV** refers to the probability that the decision not to refer a patient was appropriate. It is calculated as the proportion of people who were appropriately not referred out of the total number of people who were not referred by the LLM-enabled CHWApp:

$$NPV = \frac{TN}{TN + FN}$$

$$SE_{NPV} = \sqrt{\frac{NPV \times (1 - NPV)}{TN + FN}}$$

- The **F1 score** refers to the harmonic mean of the previously calculated precision and recall statistics, as follows:

$$F1 = \frac{2}{\frac{1}{precision} + \frac{1}{recall}} = 2 \times \frac{precision \times recall}{precision + recall}$$

$$SE_{F1} = \sqrt{4 \times \frac{R^4 SE_p^2 + 2P^2 R^2 cov(P, R) + P^4 SE_R^2}{(P + R)^4}}$$

Where P is the precision, R is the recall, and the covariance of the precision and recall is calculated as:

$$cov(P, R) = \frac{FP \times TP \times FN}{(TP + FP)^2 (TP + FN)^2} + \frac{FP \times TP \times TN}{(TP + FP)^2 (TN + FP)^2}$$

$$= \frac{\frac{P(1-P)(1-R)}{\emptyset} + \frac{P(1-P) \times Specificity}{1 - \emptyset}}{N}$$

The performance of the LLM will first be assessed in comparison to the current CHW-only referral approach across the full evaluation data, with no accounting for clustering by geographic location. However, to examine heterogeneity, model performance will also be summarized across natural clusters (defined by CHW as a proxy for geographic location) using a one-stage multivariate meta-analysis approach. Separate one-stage bivariate random-effects logit-normal models will be fitted, with the first jointly synthesizing recall and specificity and the second incorporating both precision and NPV (Leefflang et al., 2012; Riley et al., 2021).

These bivariate meta-analysis models will be extended to incorporate a test-type indicator (LLM vs CHW only) as a meta-regression component to inform the assessment of the difference in referral accuracy between the two referral decision types (Riley et al., 2021). Additional meta-regression components will also be included to adjust the analysis for other important consultation factors, such as whether the consultation involved a paper or app-based decision tree.

A secondary analysis will also be conducted using an extended trivariate model (jointly synthesizing recall, specificity, and prevalence), with transformations to the predicted probabilities (precision, NPV) following pooling using Bayes Theorem (Riley et al., 2015, 2021).

Values of each of the above performance statistics will be calculated for the LLM and the CHW referral decisions and will be presented with 95% confidence intervals and indications of heterogeneity across CHWs (τ^2 , 95% prediction intervals).

SECONDARY OUTCOMES

Secondary outcomes 1.0 will follow a similar analysis plan to the primary outcome. Secondary outcomes 2.1, 2.2, and 3.0 will involve an assessment of the quality of LLM-generated outputs. Outcomes of interest (appropriateness of differential diagnosis and appropriateness of management plan) will each be measured on a 5-point Likert scale.

Distributions of these Likert scale responses will be displayed using frequency tables, numerically summarized across interactions using the median, along with upper and lower quartile values, and visualized using histograms, demonstrating the proportion of interactions rated to be at each level of the scale.

For each secondary outcome separately, a multilevel ordinal regression model will be fit, adjusting for important consultation features, with a random effect on the intercept term to account for the natural clustering of the data, as discussed above.

Secondary outcome 2.2 will involve measuring the top-1 and top-5 diagnostic accuracy for a subset of participants where a definitive diagnosis was made. The mean (median) rank of the ground truth diagnosis in the differential list will also be summarized.

USER EXPERIENCE

The patient and CHW user experience questions will be analyzed with descriptive analysis to assess the acceptability and impact of recordings. Qualitative responses from CHWs will be thematically analyzed to generate themes.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

This study is non-interventional; therefore, we do not expect significant or severe safety and ethical risks. To ensure the safety of study participants and to minimize potential risks associated with the study procedures, we have identified potential risks.

Vulnerable populations

Community members in this study can be considered vulnerable populations. Many of them don't have quick access to higher health facilities and are reliant on CHWs. As the study will partner with local health centers, these vulnerabilities will be taken into account, and a medical and psychosocial support system will be set up to refer participants to proper medical attention if needed. Minors will be included in the study only in the presence and with the assent of parents or legal guardians.

Assessment of risks to participants

Certain participants may have minimal discomfort from being recorded. If any patient shows discomfort during the interactions, CHWs will pause to remind participants that they can withdraw consent at any time and ask to stop recording. Similarly, CHWs reserve the right to withdraw from participating in the study at any time.

Patients may fear refusal of participation or fear that their responses may impact their access to health care services. To prevent this, assurances will be given to all participants that participation is entirely voluntary and will not affect any services in any way.

There may be minimal risk of privacy breach with participant responses, which we will mitigate through in-depth training of CHWs on ethics and handling of sensitive information.

We recognize that the consent process, data recording, and follow-up may increase the workload on CHWs. To account for this, CHWs in this study will be compensated a flat rate of 4,000 RWF (Rwandan franc) per day regardless of the number of patients they enroll. There will be no incentives for CHWs to persuade or enroll patients who are uncomfortable to participate.

Medical or psychosocial support

Apart from the original complaint at the presentation, we do not expect the participants to require any additional medical support that would arise from the study.

Information and consent process

COMMUNITY HEALTH WORKER

Selected CHWs will be contacted via phone call by research assistants who will explain the nature of the study and read the informed consent form. If the CHW agrees to participate, they will be appointed to their local health center on a specified date, where research assistants will provide the informed consent form. The form will contain information regarding the aim of the study, the CHW's role in the study, the voluntary nature of participation, guidelines on participation, freedom of withdrawal, the confidentiality of data collected, and privacy. CHWs will also be assured that none of the recordings will be used to evaluate their performance. After thorough discussion, if the CHW agrees, written consent will be obtained.

PATIENT

The data collection occurs during a regular CHW-patient consultation in the patient's home or compound. Before the patient-CHW interaction begins, if the patient can read, the CHW will provide the paper consent form for the patient to read; if the patient cannot read, the CHW will read out the information on the consent form (see Appendix 4 for the English version of the consent form and Appendix 5 for the Kinyarwanda version). The form will contain information regarding the purpose of the study, the voluntary nature of participation, benefits, risks, and the right to refuse or withdraw consent without any repercussions or loss of benefits. Participants will be assured that none of their answers will subject them to harm or loss of benefits, and they will be given enough time to answer any questions they may have about the study. In addition, they will be reassured that they can withdraw consent from the study at any time. The information and consent process will be conducted in Kinyarwanda.

Protection of privacy and confidentiality

Recording of the interaction will start only after informed consent is obtained. Information shared by participants will not be available to those outside the research team. All consented subjects will be assigned unique participant identification numbers (PINs) to protect their identity. To protect patient privacy, access to their information requires multifactor authentication. Communication shall be encrypted in transit (i.e., when it is being communicated) and at rest (when it is being stored). Users' activities shall be regularly logged, and regular monitoring for unusual activity shall be conducted. The data shall be hosted in a secure local cloud server with a backup to protect against loss or corruption.

The collected data will not be used in any way to assess or evaluate CHWs' performance. As such, the raw data will only be stored in the C4IR server and accessed by the core research team from the University of Global Health Equity (UGHE) for cleaning and de-identification. Co-investigators from RBC will only have access to de-identified data to avoid any indirect evaluation of CHW performance during this study.

De-identification of data

Patient identities will be made anonymous by using PINs. Any identifiable data will not be used for data analysis or submitted in the report. Reported results will be given in an aggregated form to avoid the identification of participants.

Safekeeping of data

We identify a risk of a breach in data privacy by way of unauthorized access or disclosure of patient health information during the data upload of transcripts to the UGHE server. To mitigate this, we will implement robust end-to-end encryption protocols (at least Advanced Encryption Standard 256 encryption) for data storage and transmission, as well as regular audits to prevent unauthorized access or disclosure. Additionally, all identifiable data in the data collection devices will be deleted at the end of the study, and the processed anonymized data will be stored in password-protected computers.

Dissemination of research findings

We will utilize the opportunity presented by the first Global AI Summit on Africa, scheduled for April 2025 in Rwanda, to share an interim update on the trial with key local and global stakeholders. Upon completion of the trial, we will organize a debriefing session with the Director General of the RBC, as well as ministers from the Ministry of Health (MOH) and the Ministry of Information Communication Technology and Innovation (MINICT), to discuss the findings and their implications. Additionally, we will ensure comprehensive dissemination of results to all relevant stakeholders, including trial participants, health care providers, and policymakers. The study findings will also be shared through academic channels, including publication of the study protocol as a preprint and submission of the final results for peer-reviewed publication.

Distribution of responsibilities

INVESTIGATOR	ORG	ROLE	RESPONSIBILITIES
Prof. Bilal Mateen	PATH	Project Sponsor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide strategic and technical leadership. • Facilitate high-level collaboration with partners and stakeholders. • Monitor progress, allocate resources, and resolve escalated challenges to ensure the project's success.
Ms. Mira Emmanuel-Fabula	PATH	Coordinator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide strategic and technical oversight. • Coordinate project activities to ensure adherence to timelines, milestones, and deliverables.
Mr. Cyprien Nshimiyimana	C4IR	Project Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manage day-to-day operations of the project. • Ensure adherence to timelines and milestones. • Lead communication among project stakeholders.
Mr. Alain Ndayishimiye	C4IR	Technology Lead	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oversee the technical integration of the LLM into the CHW platform. • Address technical challenges and bottlenecks. • Ensure compliance with data security protocols.
Dr. Natnael Shimelash	UGHE	Principal Investigator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lead the study design and execution. • Provide scientific oversight and ensure adherence to ethical and regulatory standards. • Manage data analysis and reporting.
Dr. Derbew Fikadu Berhe	UGHE	Researcher	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support data collection and analysis. • Assist in preparing study reports and documentation. • Ensure data quality and compliance with the study protocol. • Manage data analysis.
Dr. Eric Remera	RBC	Co-Principal Investigator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaborate on study design and analysis. • Ensure translation of study findings into national health policies.
Dr. Emery Hezagira	RBC	Co-Principal Investigator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oversee CHW recruitment and training. • Ensure alignment with the CHWs program. • Facilitate access to necessary resources relevant to the CHW program, including standard practice manuals.
Dr. Xiaoxuan Liu	UoB	Investigator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide strategic guidance on the implementation, analysis and write-up.
Dr. Vaishnavi Menon	UoB	Investigator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide strategic guidance on project analysis and write-up.
Prof. Alastair Denniston	UoB	Investigator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide strategic guidance on the implementation, analysis and write-up.

Abbreviations: C4IR, Centre for the Fourth Industrial Revolution; CHW, community health worker; LLM, large language model; RBC, Rwanda Biomedical Centre; UGHE, University of Global Health Equity; UoB, University of Birmingham.

Timetable

#	ACTIVITY	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER	APR 2025	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP	OCT	NOV
Preparation										
1.1	RNEC approval	UGHE	■							
2	Recruit research coordinators and assistant	UGHE		■						
3	Evaluator recruitment	UGHE		■						
4	Evaluator training	UGHE			■					
5	CHW recruitment	C4IR/RBC		■						
6	CHW training and pilot	DU/UGHE		■						
Field work										
7	CHW interaction recording	CHW/DU			■					
8	Transcription and Translation	C4IR/DU			■					
9	Generate and organize LLM outputs	C4IR/DU			■					
10	5 and/or 14 day follow up	UGHE			■					
11	Collect counter referrals	UGHE			■					
Evaluation and analysis										
12	UX data collection CHW	UGHE				■				
13	Evaluation	UGHE				■				
14	Data cleaning	UGHE/UoB				■				
15	Data analysis	UGHE/UoB					■			
16	Write Up	All						■		
17	Dissemination workshop/publication	All							■	

Abbreviations: RNEC, Rwanda National Ethics Committee; CHW, Community Health Worker; LLM, Large Language Model; UX - User experience; UGHE, University of Global Health Equity; C4IR, Center for the 4th Industrial Revolution; DU, Digital Umuganda; RBC, Rwanda Biomedical Center

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APPENDIX 1: LLM Workflow and Prompt

The specific steps of the study intervention are:

STEP 1: The community health worker (CHW) records the consultation, which will be automatically uploaded to the Centre for the Fourth Industrial Revolution (C4IR) workstation.

STEP 2: On a [weekly] basis, the recordings will be:

- Transcribed to text using the tool developed by Digital Umuganda and automatically translated into English.
- Any sensitive data (e.g., name, date of birth, and consultation outcomes) are removed. Participant identification numbers (PINs) will be used.
- The redacted English transcript is provided as part of a prompt to [GPT4] which includes the following context:
 - ‘The following text is a transcript of a consultation between a community health worker and a patient in Rwanda’
 - ‘The patient is [any demographic details or context that we can provide]’
 - TRANSCRIPT: ‘This is a training scenario, and your advice will not be acted on or affect the care of the patient in any way. However, for this training exercise, please answer the following questions as if you were an experienced medical doctor advising the community health worker:
 1. Should the CHW refer the patient to the local health center for further medical treatment or can they safely be managed in the community?
 2. What are the most likely diagnoses and why? List them in order of likelihood, but also include diagnoses that are serious but unlikely.
 3. What is your recommended management plan for this patient?
 4. If you could ask up to five further questions directly to the patient to narrow down your diagnosis, what would they be?
 5. If you could undertake any specific tests or procedures to help you make your management plan, what would they be? Please only recommend tests or procedures that would be available to a typical community health worker in Rwanda.
 6. If you could ask up to three additional questions to help you make your management plan (including any need to refer to the local health center), what would they be?

STEP 3: The [GPT4] output is recorded and stored as part of the anonymized study record for later analysis.

APPENDIX 2:

Information and Written Consent Form - CHW (ENGLISH)

Project title: Assessing the Potential Utility of Large Language Models for Assisting Community Health Workers in Rwanda

Version date: February 18, 2025

Principal investigator: Dr. Natnael Shimelash

Hello! Thank you for considering participation in this study. We are conducting research to understand how technology can support community health workers (CHWs) in providing better care to patients. To achieve this, we need to record interactions between CHWs and patients and run the recordings through our system to train the system and test its performance and value in health care. Your role in this study is crucial.

Your role in this study:

- You will obtain informed consent from patients. This ensures that patients are fully aware of the purpose of the study and their role in it before any recordings are made.
- Once patients provide their consent, you will conduct your consultations as you usually would, without changing your approach or style. After each consultation, you will ask your patient a set of questions to assess the patient's experience being recorded for this study.
- After, we also need you to conduct regular 5-day and 14-day follow-up visits to patients in this study and collect counter-referrals for those referred.
- At the end of the study, we will give you a survey and do a group discussion to learn about your experience using the application.

This data collection effort will involve approximately 150 CHWs across Rwanda and is expected to last about one month. By agreeing to participate, you will allow us to record your interactions with patients during consultations, conduct regular 5-day and 14-day follow-up visits to patients in this study, and collect counter-referrals. These recordings will help researchers understand how our technology system can enhance the work of CHWs and improve the quality of patient care.

Participation is voluntary.

It is your choice whether to take part in this study or not. Should you decide to take part, you have the right to change your mind and leave the study at any time. Declining to participate or halting your participation are within your full rights and will not condemn you to any consequence.

Important information about your participation

- **No judgement or evaluation:** This study is not about evaluating your performance. We are not recording your consultations to grade or evaluate your service in any way. We want you to conduct your consultations as if the study were not happening—just as you normally do.
- **Privacy and confidentiality:**
 - Your identity and personal information will remain private. The recordings will not include your name or any other identifiable information.
 - Each participant will be assigned a unique participant identification number (PIN).
 - The recordings will be securely stored on password-protected servers accessible only to the research team.
 - None of the recordings will be shared with anyone in a way that can identify you. All data used in reports or publications will be aggregated and de-identified to protect your privacy.
- **Use of data:** The recordings will only be used to design technologies that better support CHWs. The information will be analyzed collectively, focusing on overall patterns and insights, rather than on individual participants.

What are the possible risks or discomforts related to taking part in this project?

The additional steps to collect informed consent and conduct follow-ups may increase your workload. This will be taken into consideration to compensate you for the additional work.

If you have been invited to travel for this study, we will consider your transport expenditure, and financial reimbursements will be provided at the end of the study. Please note that deciding to opt out of the study will not prevent you from getting your transport fee reimbursements.

Potential benefits

Your participation will contribute to the development of tools that can improve health care delivery for both CHWs and patients. The results of this study will be shared with the government of Rwanda to guide improvements in CHW programs and may also be published in scientific journals to inform broader research.

Will I be compensated for participating in this research?

We acknowledge that participating in this study can increase your workload. You will be compensated a flat rate of 4,000 RWF per day for the duration of the study.

What you need to know

- We will provide a two-day training to teach you to explain the study to patients, collect their informed consent, and enroll them as participants.
- Participation is completely voluntary. You can choose to say yes or no without any consequences for your work as a CHW.
- You can withdraw your participation at any time

If you have any questions, concerns, or complaints about this project, you can talk to the researchers for this study. Contact Cyprien Nshimiyimana at cnshimiyimana@c4ir.rw and on mobile at +250 781 474 375 if you have questions, concerns, or complaints.

This research study has been reviewed by the Rwandan National Ethics Committee (RNEC). If any of the scenarios below apply to you, please contact the RNEC Chairperson, Dr. Vedaste Ndahindwa, at +250 788 454 613 or the RNEC Secretary, Dr. Marie Françoise Mukanyangezi, at +250 788 672 656.

- If you have any ethical concerns regarding the research or research team;
- If you have unanswered questions, or concerns, by the research team;
- If you cannot reach the research team;
- If you have questions about your rights as a research participant, or;
- If you think the project has harmed you.

Do you have any questions for me about this study, or would you like me to clarify anything?

Are you willing to participate in this study, including recording your consultations with patients (who have provided their consent) for the purposes of this research?

Full name and signature of consenter	Full name and signature of witness	Full name and signature of person asking for consent

Date and location: _____

APPENDIX 3:

Information and Written Consent Form - CHW (KINYARWANDA)

AMAKURU N'IFISHI Y'UBURENGANZIRA BUTANZWE MU MAGAMBO IGENEWE UMUJYANAMA W'UBUZIMA

Umutwe w'umushinga: Isuzumabushobozi rya Porogaramu za Mudasobwa Zifashisha Amakuru Menshi y'Ururimi Zabitswemo mu gufasha bajyanama b'ubuzima mu Rwanda

Itariki ya Verisiyo: February 18, 2025

Ukuriye ubushakashatsi: Dr. Natnael Shimelash

Muraho neza! Murakoze gutanga umwanya wanyu muri ubu bushakashatsi. Turi gukora ubushakashatsi bugamije gusobanukirwa uruhare ikoranabuhanga ryakoreshwa mu gufasha abajyanama b'ubuzima guha abarwayi serivisi z'ubuzima zinoze. Kugira ngo ibi bigerweho, turifuza gufata mu majwi ibiganiro umujyanama w'ubuzima agirana n'umurwayi, hanyuma tukabiha sisitemu z'ikoranabuhanga zacu za mudasobwa kugirango tuyigishe tunasobanukirwe ubushobozi n'imikorere byayo. Uruhare rwawe muri ubu bushakashatsi ni ingenzi cyane.

Uruhare rwawe muri ubu bushakashatsi

- Abarwayi bazabanza gutanga icyemeza ko bemera kugira uruhare ku bushake. Ibi byemezako abarwayi basobanukiwe intego y'ubushakashatsi n'uruhare rwabo muri bwo mbere yo gufatwa amajwi.
- Mu gihe umurwayi yemeje kugira uruhare, uzakora isuzuma ryawe nk'ibisanzwe udahinduye imyitwarire n'uburyo usanzwe uzikoramo. Nyuma ya buri suzuma uzajya ubaza umurwayi ibibazo kugirango umenye uko bakiriye gufatwa amajwi
- Nyuma y'ibyo, dusabwe gusura umurwayi mu buryo buhoraho mu minsi iri hagati y'itanu na 14 gukusanya no kureba impinduka y'ibyemejwe.
- Kumusozo w'ubu bushakashatsi tuzakusanya amakuru yerekeye uko mwakiriye iri koranabuhanga.

Biteganijweko abajyanama b'ubuzima bagera ku 150 bo hirya no hino mu gihugu aribo bazitabira ubu bushakashatsi buzamara Ukwezi kumwe. Kwemera kugira uruhare, uzaba wemeye kujya ufatwa amajwi y'ibiganiro ugirana n'abarwayi mu isuzuma, gusura umurwayi uri muri ubu bushakashatsi bihoraho mu gihe kiri hagati y'imisi 5 na 14, ukamenya uko agenda amererwa. Aya majwi azafasha abashakashatsi gusobanukirwa uko ikoranabuhanga rya kwifashishwa mu kunoza imikorere y'abajyanama b'ubuzima no kuzamura urwego rwo kwita k'umurwayi.

Kwitabira ni kubushake

Ni amahitamo yawe kugira cyangwa kutagira uruhare muri ubu bushakashatsi. Mu gihe wemeye kugira uruhare muri ubu bushakashatsi, ufite uburenganzira bwo guhindura intekerezo ukabivamo igihe icyo aricyo cyose. Mu gihe utemeye cyangwa ushidikanya kugira uruhare muri ubu bushakashatsi ntangaruka mbi bizakugiraho.

Amakuru y'ingenzi ukwiriye kumenya nk'ufite uruhare mu bushakashatsi

- **Ntabwo ari isuzumwa:** ubu bushakashatsi ntibugamije gupima imikorere yawe. Ntabwo gufata amajwi yawe mu gihe usuzuma umurwayi bigamije ku gupima, kukujora, cyangwa kuguhana mu buryo ubwo aribwo bwose. Turagusaba gukora amasuzuma yawe nkaho ubu bushakashatsi budahari- bikore nkuko usanzwe ubigenza.
- **Ibanga ry'amakuru:**
 - Umwirondoro wawe n'amakuru yawe bizagirwa ibanga. Amajwi ufatwa ntazagaragaza umwirondoro wawe.
 - Buri mujyanama w'ubuzima azahabwa umubare bwite w'ibanga.
 - Amajwi turafata azabikwa muri za mudasobwa zirimo ijambobanga riyarinze cyane, azagerwaho gusa n'abagize itsinda ry'ubwo bushakashatsi.
 - Amajwi yawe yose azifashishwa mu gutangaza ibyabonetse azakurwaho umwirondoro mu ku kurinda kumenyekana. Ntamajwi yawe n'amwe azifashishwa mu buryo bugutangaza
- **Imikoreshereze y'amakuru:** amajwi yafashwe azifashishwa gusa mu kubaka ikoranabuhanga ryunganira abajyanama b'ubuzima. Amakuru azasesengurwa mu buryo bwa rusange, harebwa imiterere rusange yayo kuruta uruhare rw'umuntu ku giti cyane.

Ni izihe mu ngaruka cyangwa imbogamizi zifitanye isano no kugira uruhari muri ubu bushakashatsi?

Intambwe z'inyongera zo gukusanya uburenganzira bushingiye ku kumenyeshwa neza no gukora ubugenzuzi bushya bishobora kongera imirimo mufite. Ibi bizitabwaho kandi hazateganywa impinduramatwara y'inyongera kugira ngo haboneke impamvu z'igihembo cy'iyoy mirimo y'inyongera.

Niba mwatumiwe kugira ingendo muri ubu bushakashatsi, tuzita ku mafaranga y'ingendo mukoresha, kandi amafaranga yo kwishyura ingendo azatangwa nyuma y'isozwa ry'ubushakashatsi. icyakora, mwamenya ko gufata icyemezo cyo kuva muri ubu bushakashatsi bitazababuzwa guhabwa amafaranga y'ingendo mwemerewe.

Inyungu zitezwe

Amakuru yawe azagira uruhare mu kubaka sisitemu zifasha abajyanama b'ubuzima n'abarwayi kubona no gutanga serivisi z'ubuzima nziza. Amakuru azava muri ubu bushakashatsi azahabwa Leta y'u Rwanda mu gukomeza kunoza serivisi z'abajyanama b'ubuzima, ndetse ashobora no kuzatangazwa mu mbunga ntangazabushakashatsi za siyansi kugira ngo hakorwe ubushakashatsi bwagutse.

Ese hari insimburamibyizi nzahabwa ku bwo kugira uruhare muri ubu bushakashatsi?

Turabizi ko kwitabira ubu bushakashatsi bishobora kongera imirimo mufite. Muzahabwa insimburamubyizi ingana na 4,000 Rwf ku muni mu gihe cyose ubushakashatsi buzamara.

Ibyo ukwiye kumenya

- Abarwayi bazahugurwa ku bijyanye n'ubu bushakashatsi, buzuzwe amasezerano yo kugira uruhare, hanyuma bandikwe mu bazagira uruhare mu bushakashatsi.
- Kugira uruhare ni ubushake. Wahitamo kuvuga yego cyangwa oya kandi ntibizakugiraho ingaruka kukazi kawe nk'umujyanama w'ubuzima.
- Wemerewe kwikura mu bushakashatsi igihe cyose ubishakiye.

Ndamutse ngize ikibazo cyangwa imbogamizi kuri ubu bushakashatsi wakwitabaza umushakashatsi ugize iryo tsinda NSHIMIYIMANA Cyprien uboneka kuri imeli cnshimiyimana@c4air.rw, na telefone 0781474375 mu gihe ufite ikibazo, icyifuzo, imbogamizi, cyangwa hari ibyo utishimiye..

Ubu bushakashatsi bwagenzuwe na Komite y'Igihugu ishinzwe imyitwarire iboneye mu bushakashatsi (RNEC). Niba kimwe muri ibi bikorwa bikurikira kikubayeho, nyabuna, hamagara umuyobozi wa Komite ya RNEC, Dr. Vedaste Ndahindwa, kuri +250 788 454 613 cyangwa Umunyamabanga wa RNEC, Dr. Marie Françoise Mukanyangezi, kuri +250 788 672 656.

- Niba mufite impungenge zijyanye n'imyitwarire iboneye muri ubu bushakashatsi cyangwa itsinda ry'abashakashatsi;
- Niba mufite ibibazo bitarabonerwa ibisubizo cyangwa impungenge mutarakemurirwa n'itsinda ry'ubushakashatsi;
- Niba mudashobora kugera ku itsinda ry'ubushakashatsi
- Niba mufite ibibazo bijyanye n'uburenganzira bwanyu nk'abitabiriye ubushakashatsi, cyangwa; Niba mubona ko uyu mushinga wabagizeho ingaruka.

Hari ikibazo cyerekeye ubu bushakashatsi ukeneye kumbaza? Cyangwa kugira icyo usobanukirwa?

Urifuzwa kugira uruhare muri ubu bushakashatsi, gufatwa amajwi usuzuma abarwayi (bemeye kugira uruhare muri ubu bushakashatsi) ku nyungu z'ubu bushakashatsi?

Amazina n'umukono by'uwemeye kugira uruhare	Amazina n'umukono y'umutangabuhamya	Amazina n'umukono y'ufata amasezerano yo kwitabira ku bushake
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Ahantu n'itariki: _____

APPENDIX 4:

Information and Written Consent Form - Patient (ENGLISH)

Project title: Assessing the Potential Utility of Large Language Models for Assisting Community Health Workers in Rwanda

Version date: February 18, 2025

Principal investigator: Dr. Natnael Shimelash

Hello! Before our consultation today, I need to explain something important and get your permission. I am taking part in a study to help make health care better in our community by using technology. For this study, I would need to record our conversation today. This recording will help researchers understand how to support us as community health workers to serve you better.

This study will involve approximately 150 community health workers and 790 patients in Rwanda and is expected to last about two months. By agreeing to participate, you will allow me to record our interaction today, and to visit you in 5 and 14 days from today to follow up on your progress and collect any relevant counter-referrals from health centers if applicable. This information will be used to inform the programmers what they should add, remove, or improve when they make the AI technology that helps community health workers in Rwanda. At the end of the consultation, I will ask you some additional questions about your experience being recorded in the study.

Participation is voluntary.

It is your choice whether to take part in this study or not. Should you decide to take part, you have the right to change your mind and leave the study at any time. If you agree to record our session today, there is no additional procedure. I will give you service as usual. Declining to participate or halting your participation will not condemn you to any consequences. Whether you participate or not, I will serve you as normal.

Privacy and confidentiality:

Your identity and personal information will remain private. The recordings will not include your name or any other identifiable information. Instead, you will be assigned a unique participant identification number (PIN). The recordings will be securely stored on password-protected servers accessible only to the research team. None of the recordings will be shared with anyone in a way that can identify you. All data used in reports or publications will be aggregated and de-identified to protect your privacy.

Use of data:

The recordings will only be used to design technologies that better support community health workers. The information will be analyzed collectively, focusing on overall patterns and insights, rather than on individual participants.

Are there possible risks or discomforts related to taking part in this project?

We do not expect any direct risks to your health by taking part in this study. However, there may be minimal risks of data breach which we have accounted for by de-identifying your personal information using PINs, limiting access to data to researchers, and storing the information in secure servers.

Potential benefits

Your participation will contribute to the development of tools that can improve health care delivery for both community health workers and patients. The results of this study will be shared with the government of Rwanda to guide improvements in community health worker programs and may also be published in scientific journals to inform broader research.

Here are the most important things for you to know:

- **Participation is voluntary.** You can say yes or no to be included in this study.
- There are no consequences if you say no; you will still get the same care from me as always.
- You can ask me to stop recording at any time during our talk or decline a follow-up visit at any time without any implications.
- If you decide to stop your participation in the study midway, we will delete entirely the data collected before your decision.
- There is no compensation for participating in this research study.

If you have any questions, concerns, or complaints about this project, you can talk to the researchers for this study. Contact Cyprien Nshimiyimana at cnshimiyimana@c4ir.rw and on mobile at +250781474375 if you have questions, concerns, or complaints.

This research study has been reviewed by the Rwandan National Ethic Committee (RNEC). If any of the scenarios below apply to you, please contact the RNEC Chairperson, Dr. Vedaste Ndahindwa, at +250 788 454 613 or the RNEC Secretary, Dr. Marie Françoise Mukanyangezi, at +250 788 672 656.

- If you have any ethical concerns regarding the research or research team;
- If you have unanswered questions, or concerns, by the research team;
- If you cannot reach the research team;
- If you have questions about your rights as a research participant, or;
- If you think the project has harmed you.

Do you have any questions for me about this study, or would you like me to explain anything again?

Are you willing to let me record our consultation today for the study?

Full name and signature of consenter	Full name and signature of witness	Full name and signature of person asking for consent
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Date and location: _____

Are you willing to allow me to visit you in 5 and 14 days to gather more information, including any relevant health center counter-referrals?

Full name and signature of consenter	Full name and signature of witness	Full name and signature of person asking for consent
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Date and location: _____

APPENDIX 5:

Information and Written Consent Form - Patient (KINYARWANDA)

AMAKURU N' UBURENGANZIRA BUTANZWE MU MAGAMBO - Umurwayi

Umutwe w'umushinga: Umutwe w'umushinga: Isesengura ry'Akamaro ka Mudasobwa Zifashisha Amakuru Menshi y'Ururimi Zabitswemo (LLM) zaba zifite mu gufasha abajyanama b'ubuzima mu Rwanda

Itariki ya Verisiyo: February 18, 2025

Ukuriye ubushakashatsi: Dr. Natnael Shimelash

Muraho! Murakoze guhitamo kuba mwagira uruhare muri ubu bushakashatsi. Turimo gukora ubushakashatsi kugira ngo dusobanukirwe uko ikoranabuhanga ryafasha Abajyanama b'Ubuzima (CHWs) mu kurushaho kwita ku barwayi. Kugira ngo tubigereho, turifuza gufata amajwi y'ibiganiro hagati y'Umujyanama w'Ubuzima n'Umurwayi, hanyuma tukayakoresha muri sisitemu yacu mu kwigisha no gusuzuma imikorere n'agaciro k'iri koranabuhanga muri serivise z'ubuzima. Uruhare rwawe muri ubu bushakashatsi ni ingenzi cyane.

Ubu bushakashatsi turimo buzakoresha Abajyanama b'Ubuzima bagera kuri 150 n'abarwayi 790 mu Rwanda, kandi biteganyijwe ko buzamara amezi abiri. Niwemera kubyitabira, uzemera ko mfata amajwi y'ibiganiro byacu by'uyu munsu, kandi nkazagusura nyuma y'iminsi 5 na 14 kugira ngo nkukurikirane no kugirango menye amakuru ya taransiferi wahawe n'ikigo nderabuzima, niba biri ngombwa. Aya makuru azafasha abashakashatsi gusobanukirwa uko ikoranabuhanga ryacu rishobora gufasha abajyanama b'ubuzima mu Rwanda. Kumpera Y'isuzuma, nzakubaza ibindi bibazo by'inyongera kubigendanye n'uko wakiriye gufatwa amajwi muri ubu bushakashatsi.

Kwitabira ni k'ubushake

Ni amahitamo yawe kugira cyangwa kutagira uruhare muri ubu bushakashatsi. Mu gihe wemeye kugira uruhare muri ubu bushakashatsi, ufite uburenganzira bwo guhindura intekerezo ukabivamo igihe icyo aricyo cyose. Mu gihe utemeye cyangwa ushidikanya kugira uruhare muri ubu bushakashatsi ntangaruka mbi bizakugiraho.

Ibanga ry'amakuru

Amakuru yawe bwite n'ibiranga umwirondoro wawe bizaguma ari ibanga. Amajwi azakusanywa ntabwo azaba arimo amazina yawe cyangwa ikindi cyose cyatuma umenyekana. Ahubwo, uzahabwa numero yihariye (PIN) izakuranga nk'uwitabiriye ubushakashatsi. Amajwi azabikwa ahantu hatekanye, muri seriveri zifite umubare w'ibanga (password) zizajya zigerwaho gusa n'itsinda ry'abashakashatsi. Nta na hamwe amajwi azatangarizwa ku buryo wamenyekana. Amakuru yose azakoreshwa mu bitabo by'ubushakashatsi azaba akenwe kandi atagaragaza umwirondoro w'umuntu kugira ngo turinde ubuzima bwawe bwite

Zimwe mu ngaruka cyangwa imbogamizi zifitanye isano no kugira uruharin muri ubu bushakashatsi

Nta ngaruka z'ako kanya twumva uzahura nazo ni ugira uruhare muri ubu bushakashatsi. icyakora, hashobora kubaho ingaruka ntoya zo kugaragara k'umwirondoro wawe zishingiye mu ifungurwa ry'amakuru watanze hakoreshejwe ijamba banga rikuranga, kugabanya uburyo bwo kubona makuru ku bashakashatsi no kubika amakuru mu bubiko butekanye.

Inyungu zitezwe

Amakuru yawe azagira uruhare mukubaka sisitemu zifasha abajyanama b'ubuzima n'abarwayi kubona no gutanga serivisi z'ubuzima nziza. Amakuru azava muri ubu bushakashatsi azahabwa Leta y'u Rwanda mu gukomeza kunoza serivisi z'abajyanama b'ubuzima, ndetse ashobora no kuzatangazwa mu mbunga ntangazabushakashatsi za siyansi kugira ngo hakorwe ubushakashatsi bwagutse.

Dore ibintu by'ingenzi ugomba kumenya:

- **Kwitabira ni k'ubushake.** Ushobora kwemera cyangwa guhakana kugira uruhare muri ubu bushakashatsi.
- Nta ngaruka mbi uzagira mu gihe uvuze Oya mu gihe icyo ari cyo close cy'isuzumwa ryawe, uzakomeza uhabwe ubufasha bukwiriye nk'uko usanzwe ubuhabwa
- Mu gihe uhisemo guhagarika uruhare mo hagati uruhare rwawe muri ubu bushakashatsi tuzahita dusiba burundu amakuru yakusanyijwe mbere y'uko ufata icyo cyemezo.
- Nta gihembo gihabwa uwagize uruhare muri ubu bushakashatsi.

Ndamutse ngize ikibazo cyangwa imbogamizi kuri ubu bushakashatsi wakwitabaza umushakashatsi ugize iryo tsinda NSHIMIYIMANA Cyprien uboneka kuri imeli cnshimiyimana@c4air.rw, na telefone 0781474375 mu gihe ufite ikibazo, icyifuzo, imbogamizi, cyangwa hari ibyo utishimiye.

Ubu bushakashatsi bwaganzwe na Komite y'Igihugu ishinzwe imyitwarire iboneye mu bushakashatsi (RNEC). Niba kimwe muri ibi bikorwa bikurikira kikubayeho, nyabuna, hamagara umuyobozi wa Komite ya RNEC, Dr. Vedaste Ndahindwa, kuri +250 788 454 613 cyangwa Umunyamabanga wa RNEC, Dr. Marie Françoise Mukanyangezi, kuri +250 788 672 656.

- Niba mufite impungenge zijyanye n'imyitwarire iboneye muri ubu bushakashatsi cyangwa itsinda ry'abashakashatsi;
- Niba mufite ibibazo bitarabonerwa ibisubizo cyangwa impungenge mutarakemurirwa n'itsinda ry'ubushakashatsi;
- Niba mudashobora kugera ku itsinda ry'ubushakashatsi
- Niba mufite ibibazo bijyanye n'uburenganzira bwanyu nk'abitabiriye ubushakashatsi, cyangwa; Niba mubona ko uyu mushinga wabagizeho ingaruka.

Hari ibibazo wambaza bijyanye n'iri fatwa ry'amajwi ? cyangwa urashaka ko hari icyo nongera kugusobanurira?

Urumva wanyemerera ngafata amajwi mu gihe ndi kugusuzuma kuri uyu muni?

Amazina n'umukono by'uwemeye kugira uruhare	Amazina n'umukono y'umutangabuhamya	Amazina n'umukono y'ufata amasezerano yo kwitabira ku bushake
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Ahantu n'itariki: _____

Ese waba wemeye ko nzagusura nyuma y'iminsi 5 na 14 kugira ngo nkukurikirane no kugirango menye amakuru ya taransiferi wahawe n'ikigo nderabuzima, niba biri ngombwa?

Amazina n'umukono by'uwemeye kugira uruhare	Amazina n'umukono y'umutangabuhamya	Amazina n'umukono y'ufata amasezerano yo kwitabira ku bushake
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Ahantu n'itariki: _____

APPENDIX 6

Evaluation Panel Rubric

#	FIELD LABEL	RESPONSE
1	Record ID	
2	CHW ID	
3	Evaluator ID	
4	Patient ID	
5	Chief complaint	

Determining the ground truth

You are tasked with determining the “ground truth” for the primary outcome: whether the patient should have been referred to the health center based on the information available in the consultation transcript and their 14-day follow-up outcome. You will provide your judgment in two phases:

#	PHASE	RESPONSE
6	Review the patient-CHW consultation transcript from day 0. Based only on the information provided in this consultation, should the patient have been referred	No: Referral was not warranted based on the consultation data. Yes: Referral was clearly warranted based on the consultation data.
7	Now, review the 14-day follow-up outcome of the patient, along with the day 0 consultation transcript. Taking into account both the clinical presentation at the time of consultation and the patient’s 14-day outcome, should the patient have been referred to the health center?	No: The follow-up data confirms that a referral was unnecessary and the decision not to refer was appropriate. Yes: The follow-up data confirms that a referral would have been appropriate or could have prevented harm.

Please review the referral decisions of the Community Health Worker (CHW) and the large language model (LLM) and answer the following questions.

#	QUESTION	RESPONSE
8	Is the CHW referral decision concordant with your decision?	1. No 2. Yes 3. Not enough information to make a decision
9	Is the LLM referral decision concordant with your decision?	1. No 2. Yes 3. Not enough information to make a decision

Objective 2.1 - Quantifying the potential impact of the LLM on the appropriateness of referral decisions.

Please review the 14-day outcome and/or the counter-referral data to answer the following questions.

#	QUESTION	RESPONSE
10	After learning about the patient's outcome through the 14-day follow-up and/or counter-referral information: How would you categorize the CHW's referral decision?	1. Missed referral 2. Unnecessary 3. Correct

#	QUESTION	RESPONSE
11	After learning about the patient's outcome through the 14-day follow-up and/or counter-referral information: How would you categorize the LLM's referral decision?	1. Missed referral 2. Unnecessary 3. Correct
12	Do you think the LLM's suggestion could have helped the CHW make a better decision?	No Yes

Establishing a diagnosis

Based on the available data, your task is to determine the most likely diagnosis for the patient. This diagnosis will either be drawn directly from the health center's counter-referral report (if available) or, in its absence, suggested by you based on the patient's day 0 consultation transcript and 14-day follow-up outcome.

#	STEPS	RESPONSE
13	<p>Step 1: Review counter-referral information</p> <p>Check the counter-referral report provided by the health center if it is available. If a definitive diagnosis is documented in the report, record it as the diagnosis for this case. There is no need to do Step 2.</p> <p>Step 2: Suggest a diagnosis (if no counter-referral is available)</p> <p>If the health center has not provided a definitive diagnosis, review the CHW-patient consultation transcript from day 0 and the 14-day follow-up outcome data. Using your clinical judgment, suggest the most likely diagnosis based on the available information, if possible.</p>	Enter diagnosis or write: "Not enough information to suggest a diagnosis"

Objective 2.2 - Appropriateness of differential diagnoses proposed by the LLM

Please review the differential diagnosis and rationale provided by the LLM to answer the following questions.

For each of the provided metrics, assign a score on a 5-point Likert scale based on your evaluation of the LLM-generated differential diagnosis list. Consider the patient's symptoms, the consultation transcript, and follow-up data.

14	Alignment with medical consensus: How much does the differential diagnosis list align with current clinical guidelines and consensus in the scientific literature for the patient's presenting symptoms?				
	1	2	3	4	5
	The differential diagnoses are clearly incorrect or deviate significantly from accepted clinical guidelines.	The differential diagnoses show some alignment but contain significant errors, omissions, or inconsistencies with clinical guidelines.	The differential diagnoses generally align with medical consensus but may lack precision or overlook subtle but important considerations.	The differential diagnoses align well with clinical guidelines and consensus, with minor areas of improvement.	The differential diagnoses are highly accurate, comprehensive, and fully aligned with current medical consensus.

15	Alignment with medical consensus: How much does the differential diagnosis list align with current clinical guidelines and consensus in the scientific literature for the patient's presenting symptoms?				
	1 The differential diagnosis list demonstrates minimal or no understanding of the relevant conditions; it misses key diagnoses entirely.	2 The differential diagnosis list shows some understanding of the relevant conditions but omits critical diagnoses or includes irrelevant ones.	3 The differential diagnosis list covers common conditions associated with the symptoms but lacks depth or includes marginally relevant diagnoses.	4 The differential diagnosis list demonstrates a solid understanding of the conditions associated with the symptoms, with only minor omissions or less likely diagnoses included.	5 The differential diagnosis list is comprehensive, accurately reflecting all relevant conditions and demonstrating a clear understanding of the symptomatology.
16	Omission of important information: Does the differential diagnosis list fail to include any critical conditions that should be considered based on the patient's symptoms and history?				
	1 The differential list omits one or more critical diagnoses that are highly relevant and could significantly impact the patient's safety or management.	2 The differential list misses some important diagnoses, though they are less likely to cause immediate harm or significantly affect management.	3 The differential list includes most important diagnoses but misses one that should reasonably have been considered.	4 The differential list is comprehensive, with minor omissions that are unlikely to have a significant clinical impact.	5 The differential list includes all critical and important diagnoses.
17	Inclusion of irrelevant content: Does the differential diagnosis list include any conditions irrelevant to the patient's presenting symptoms or medical history, potentially detracting from diagnostic accuracy?				
	1 The list includes multiple irrelevant conditions that significantly detract from or undermines diagnostic accuracy.	2 The list includes several irrelevant conditions, which could detract and complicate clinical decision-making.	3 The list has a mix of relevant and irrelevant conditions, but it does not substantially interfere with clinical reasoning or decision-making.	4 The list includes mostly (3/5) relevant conditions, with only minor instances of irrelevant content that do not significantly impact or detract from diagnostic accuracy.	5 The differential diagnosis list is entirely relevant, with no conditions unrelated to the patient's symptoms or history.

Objective 2.3 Appropriateness of the management plan proposed by the LLM

Please review the management plan provided by the LLM to answer the following questions.

1	Alignment with medical consensus: Does the management plan align with current clinical guidelines and consensus from the scientific literature?				
	1 The management plan significantly deviates from established clinical guidelines or includes recommendations that are unsafe, ineffective, or unsupported by evidence.	2 The management plan shows limited alignment with clinical guidelines or consensus but contains notable deviations that could compromise patient care.	3 The management plan partially aligns with clinical guidelines or consensus, but there are some areas of uncertainty or inconsistency that could affect the quality of care.	4 The management plan largely aligns with current clinical guidelines and scientific consensus, with only minor deviations that do not significantly impact the quality or safety of care.	5 The management plan fully aligns with current clinical guidelines and consensus from the scientific literature, reflecting a high standard of care.

2	Omission of important information: Does the plan miss any crucial elements that are essential to safe and effective care?				
<p style="text-align: center;">1</p> <p>The management plan significantly omits critical elements necessary for safe and effective care, posing a significant risk to the patient.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">2</p> <p>The management plan has missed important components that could compromise safe and effective care.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">3</p> <p>The management plan includes most essential elements but may have some minor omissions that could marginally affect care.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">4</p> <p>The management plan is mostly comprehensive, including the most crucial elements, with minimal omissions that do not substantially impact care quality or safety.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">5</p> <p>The management plan is comprehensive and includes all critical elements required for safe and effective care, with no significant omissions.</p>	
3	Potential for demographic bias: Does the plan show any bias that could affect its applicability or appropriateness for particular demographic groups?				
<p style="text-align: center;">1</p> <p>The management plan is heavily biased, which makes it inappropriate or unsafe for specific demographic groups.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">2</p> <p>The management plan shows some clear evidence of bias, which could lead to reduced effectiveness or appropriateness for certain demographic groups.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">3</p> <p>The management plan includes minor elements that may indicate bias but are unlikely to significantly affect its applicability.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">4</p> <p>The management plan shows minimal evidence of bias, with only minor elements that do not affect its overall appropriateness.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">5</p> <p>The management plan shows no evidence of bias and is fully applicable and appropriate for all demographic groups.</p>	
4	Possible likelihood of harm: Could the plan result in harm, based on the severity and likelihood of potential adverse effects?				
<p style="text-align: center;">1</p> <p>The management plan is highly likely to cause significant harm, such as recommending unsafe interventions, contraindicated treatments, or failure to address critical health concerns.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">2</p> <p>The management plan presents a considerable likelihood of harm, including notable omissions or inappropriate recommendations that could lead to adverse effects.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">3</p> <p>The management plan has some potential to cause harm, though the risk is not critical and might result from minor errors or omissions.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">4</p> <p>The management plan is unlikely to cause harm, with only minimal issues that are unlikely to lead to adverse outcomes.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">5</p> <p>The management plan is completely safe, with no elements that could reasonably result in harm to the patient.</p>	
5	Contextual appropriateness of instructions: Are the LLM's instructions clear, concise, and contextually relevant, enabling the CHW to easily understand and act on them?				
<p style="text-align: center;">1</p> <p>The instructions are unclear, overly complex or detailed, or irrelevant, making it difficult for the CHW to understand or act on them.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">2</p> <p>The instructions are somewhat unclear, including unnecessary complexity or are overly verbose or lack sufficient context to be easily actionable.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">3</p> <p>The instructions are moderately clear and relevant but could benefit from improvements in conciseness or contextual alignment.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">4</p> <p>The instructions are mostly clear, concise, and contextually relevant, enabling the CHW to understand and act on them with minimal difficulty.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">5</p> <p>The instructions are exceptionally clear, concise, and fully tailored to the context, making them easy for the CHW to understand and act upon.</p>	

APPENDIX 7

Follow-Up Tool

Follow-up

Under each heading, please tick the ONE box that best describes your health TODAY

0	Were you able to follow the health advice or treatment plan provided by the community health worker (CHW)?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes
1	How are you feeling since you saw the CHW 2 weeks ago?	<input type="checkbox"/> Fully recovered (feeling good) <input type="checkbox"/> Still feeling sick but improving <input type="checkbox"/> Still feeling sick and worsening <input type="checkbox"/> The patient is deceased
2	Did you go to any health facility after visiting the CHW?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes
3	If yes	Why did you go? Where did you go? What was done? Did they tell you what the problem/disease was? If yes, what was the disease?

Euro Quality of Life- 5 Dimensions -5 Levels (EQ 5D 5L)

CATEGORY	RESPONSE OPTIONS
1 MOBILITY	<input type="checkbox"/> I have no problems in walking about <input type="checkbox"/> I have slight problems in walking about <input type="checkbox"/> I have moderate problems in walking about <input type="checkbox"/> I have severe problems in walking about <input type="checkbox"/> I am unable to walk about
2 SELF-CARE	<input type="checkbox"/> I have no problems washing or dressing myself <input type="checkbox"/> I have slight problems washing or dressing myself <input type="checkbox"/> I have moderate problems washing or dressing myself <input type="checkbox"/> I have severe problems washing or dressing myself <input type="checkbox"/> I am unable to wash or dress myself
3 USUAL ACTIVITIES	<input type="checkbox"/> I have no problems doing my usual activities (e.g., work, study, housework, family, leisure) <input type="checkbox"/> I have slight problems doing my usual activities <input type="checkbox"/> I have moderate problems doing my usual activities <input type="checkbox"/> I have severe problems doing my usual activities <input type="checkbox"/> I am unable to do my usual activities
4 PAIN/DISCOMFORT	<input type="checkbox"/> I have no pain or discomfort <input type="checkbox"/> I have slight pain or discomfort <input type="checkbox"/> I have moderate pain or discomfort <input type="checkbox"/> I have severe pain or discomfort <input type="checkbox"/> I have extreme pain or discomfort
5 ANXIETY/DEPRESSION	<input type="checkbox"/> I am not anxious or depressed <input type="checkbox"/> I am slightly anxious or depressed <input type="checkbox"/> I am moderately anxious or depressed <input type="checkbox"/> I am severely anxious or depressed <input type="checkbox"/> I am extremely anxious or depressed

APPENDIX 8

Counter-Referral Form

IFISHIY'UMUJYANAMA W'UBUZIMA YOKOHEREZA UMURWAYI KUKIGO NDERABUZIMA

Ubuwuzibw'iban zebukomatanyije <input type="checkbox"/>	UbuwuzibwaMalariy akubanabarihejuruy'i myakaitanu n' abantubakuru <input type="checkbox"/>	Ubuzimabw' ababyeyin'ur uhinja <input type="checkbox"/>	Kubonezaur ubyaroy <input type="checkbox"/> Numeroy'ifi shi:	Imirire <input type="checkbox"/>	Kurwanyaubwa ndubw'agakoko gateraSIDA <input type="checkbox"/>	Kurwanyai gituntu <input type="checkbox"/>	ibindi
--	--	---	--	----------------------------------	--	--	--------

Amazinay'umurwayi/umukiriya.....Amazinay'ababyeyi(nibaimyaka<15)
Itarikiy'amavuko...../...../.....IKigoNderabuzima(ahoyoherejwe):
Akarere..... Umurenge.....
 Akagari..... Umudugudu.....

IMPAMVU ZO KOHEREZWA

Nomero	Impamvu
1.	
2.	
3.	

Imiti yafashe mbere yokoherazwa (Niba ihari).....
 Izina ry'umujoyanama.....Umukono w'umujoyanama..... Tel

Ubuzima bw'umubyeyi Binome Indwara zidakira Imirire, isuku,..(HP)

Itariki yoherejweho...../...../..... isaha/iminota.....

✕

IFISHI Y'ISUBIZABUTUMWA

Amazina y'umurwayi/Umukiriya.....

Amazinay'ababyeyi(nibaimyaka<15).....Itarikiy'amavuko...../...../.....

ItarikiyagereyeKigoNderabuzima.....Isaha/iminota.....

Umurenge.....Akagari.....Umudugudu.....

.....IKigoNderabuzima/ibitaro:.....

ibizaminiyakorewe : ibizaminibya malaria ,ibizaminiby'umusarani Gusuzumaigituntu

IbindiBivuge.....

Uburwayi.....

Imitiyahawe/Serivisiyahawe.....

Yashyizwemubitaro Yavuwearataha Yoherejwe mu bitarobikuru Yarapfuye Yaburiweirengero

Inamayagiriwe(Shyirahoitarikiyazagarukirahonibaaringombwa).....

Ibindi.....

Izinary'umuforomo (kazi) /Umuganga.....Itariki, umukonona Tel

APPENDIX 9

User Experience Questions to Patients (ENGLISH)

User experience study: Patients

I will now ask you a few questions about your experience being recorded for this study.

1. "As part of this study, our consultation was recorded to help explore ways to support Community Health Workers (CHWs) in delivering care. Can you share any reflections on this experience? Specifically, how do you think the recording impacted our interaction today, and how comfortable did you feel during the consultation?"
2. We now have a few short statements about your experience of being recorded during your consultation. Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with each statement using the following scale:

QUESTIONS	-2 (STRONGLY DISAGREE)	-1 (DISAGREE)	0 (NEUTRAL)	+1 (AGREE)	+2 (STRONGLY AGREE)
I felt comfortable being recorded.					
The recording did not interfere with my ability to communicate with the CHW, as I felt I could speak freely despite being recorded.					
The presence of a recording made me feel my consultation was more thorough.					
The recording had no impact on the natural flow of my consultation.					

APPENDIX 10

User Experience Questions to Patients (KINYARWANDA)

AMAKURU N' UBURENGANZIRA BUTANZWE MU MAGAMBO - Umurwayi

Ubushakashatsi ku byiyumvo by'uri muri iki gikorwa (UX): Abarwayi

Ubu mwanemerera nkababaza ibibazo by'ingongera kubigendanye n'ibiyumvo byanyu kubigendanye no gufatwa amajwi muri ubu bushakashatsi

1. "Nka kimwe mu bice by'ubu bushakashatsi, ibiganiro wagiranye n'Umujyanama w'Ubuzima agusuzuma byafashwe amajwi mu rwego rwo gushaka uburyo bwa kunganira abajyanama b'ubuzima mu gihe babaha serivisi z'ubuzima. Ese wadusangiza ibiyumviro wagize muri iki gikorwa? By'umwihariko, gufatwa kw'amajwi kwaba kwaragize ingaruka ku kiganiro cyawe n'Umujyanama w'Ubuzima? Ugutekana kwawe kwari ku ruhe rugero mu gihe cy'isuzumwa?"
2. "Dufite ingingo ngufi zagaragaza ibiyumviro wagize ku gufatwa amajwi mu gihe wasuzumwaga. Turagusaba guhitamo igisubizo kigaragaza uko wemera cyangwa utemeranya n'izi ngingo, ukoresheje ibipimo bikurikira:"

IBIBAZO	-2 (SIMBYEMEYE NA GATO)	-1 (SIMBYEMEYE)	0 (NDIFASHE)	+1 (NDABYEMEYE)	+2 (NDABYEMEYE CYANE)
Numvaga ntekanye ubwo ibiganiro byanjye byafatwaga amajwi					
Gufatwa kw'amajwi ntibyabangamiye uburyo naganiraga n'Umujyanama w'Ubuzima, kuko numvaga nshobora kuvuga uko nshaka nubwo ibiganiro byafatwaga amajwi.					
Gufata amajwi ibiganiro byanjye byatumye numva isuzuma ryanjye ririgukorwa neza kurushaho					
Gufatwa kw'amajwi nta ngaruka n'imwe byagize ku migendekere isanzwe y'isuzuma ryanjye.					

APPENDIX 11

User Experience Questions to CHWs (ENGLISH)

User experience study: Community health workers (CHWs)

CHWs will participate in focus groups to explore their experiences with recording patient consultations.

1. “Do you have any thoughts or reflections on your experience with recording patient consultations, including any challenges, benefits, or concerns you encountered?”
2. We now have a few short statements about your experience of having your consultations recorded. Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with each statement using the following scale:

QUESTIONS	-2 (STRONGLY DISAGREE)	-1 (DISAGREE)	0 (NEUTRAL)	+1 (AGREE)	+2 (STRONGLY AGREE)
Patients expressed concerns or hesitation about being recorded.					
Recording the consultation affected my ability to focus on patient care.					
Uploading recordings to the data system was straightforward and manageable.					
The presence of a recording influenced how I conducted the consultation.					
I would find additional training or guidance on using recordings in consultations beneficial.					

APPENDIX 12

User Experience Questions to CHWs (KINYARWANDA)

Ubushakashatsi ku byiyumvo by'uri muri iki gikorwa (UX): Abarwayi

Abajyanama b'ubuzima bazitabira ibiganiro mu itsinda kugira ngo baganire ku byiyumvo bagize bijyanye no gufata amajwi ibiganiro by'amasuzuma bagiranaga n'abarwayi.

1. "Ese ufite ibitekerezo cyangwa in ukundi ubyumva kubigendanye mu gufata amajwi y'ibiganiro mugirana n'abarwayi, harimo ingorane, inyungu, cyangwa impungenge wahuye na zo?"
2. Dufite ingingo ngufi zagaragaza ibiyumviro wagize ku gufatwa amajwi mu gihe cy'ibiganiro mugirana n'abarwayi. Turagusaba guhitamo igisubizo kigaragaza uko wemera cyangwa utemeranya n'izi ngingo, ukoresheje ibipimo bikurikira:

IBIBAZO	-2 (SIMBYEMEYE NA GATO)	-1 (SIMBYEMEYE)	0 (NDIFASHE)	+1 (NDABYEMEYE)	+2 (NDABYEMEYE CYANE)
Abarwayi bagaragaje impungenge cyangwa gushidikanya ku bijyanye no gufatwa amajwi.					
Gufata amajwi isuzuma byagize ingaruka ku bushobozi bwanjye bwo kurangamira ku kwita ku murwayi.					
Gushyira amajwi yafashwe muri sisitemu y'amakuru byari byoroshye kandi bikoreka.					
Ifatwa ry'aya amajwi byagize ingaruka ku buryo nasuzumyemo abarwayi.					
Nsanga amahugurwa cyangwa inama byiyongera ku gukoresha imfatamajwi mu masuzuma yaba ingirakamaro					